

Psychological Analysis of Procrastination as a Destructive Factor in the Formation of Professionalism

Oksana SHPORTUN¹,
Natalia AVRAMENKO²,
Vasyl KAPLINSKY³,
Tetyana KOVAL⁴,
Tamara TYURINA⁵,
Lyudmila MATOKHNIUK⁶,
Viktoriya SHEVCHUK⁷,
Ihor BLOSHCHYNSKYI⁸

¹ Doctor of psychological sciences, professor, professor of psychology department, Municipal Higher Education Institution "Vinnytsia Academy of Continuing Education", Vinnytsia, Ukraine, shportun_o@ukr.net, orcid.org/0000-0003-4528-4329

² Candidate of pedagogical sciences, lecturer of the departments of philology and humanities public, Municipal Higher Education Institution "Vinnytsia Academy of Continuing Education", Vinnytsia, Ukraine, edelnata@yahoo.de, orcid.org/0000-0003-1241-0261

³ Doctor of pedagogical sciences, associate professor, associate professor of the department of pedagogy and vocational education, Vinnytsia State Pedagogical University named after Mykhailo Kotsyubynsky, Vinnytsia, Ukraine, kaplinskiy55@mail.ru, orcid.org/0000-0003-0829-1079

⁴ Candidate of pedagogical sciences, associate professor, associate professor of the department of art disciplines of preschool and primary education, Vinnytsia State Pedagogical University named after Mykhailo Kotsyubynsky, Vinnytsia, Ukraine, tanyabyzja@ukr.net, orcid.org/0000-0001-6491-4010

Abstract: *The article actualizes the problem of psychological research features of procrastination, and definition of its influence on formation of professionalism at student's age. The psychological analysis of the concept of "procrastination" is carried out, the essence and specifics of procrastination development in student age are investigated, the level of procrastination development in student age and psychological mechanisms of its influence on formation of professionalism are investigated. The following methods were used in the study: theoretical methods (analysis of scientific and methodological literature of noctive and foreign authors in psychology); empirical methods (Scale of assessment of the need for achievements of Yu. Orlov; Methods of research of volitional self-regulation A. Zverkov, E. Eidman; Melbourne decision-making questionnaire (adaptation of T. Kornilova, S. Kornilov); Scale of procrastination for students S. Ley; Methodology "Self-assessment organization"; Questionnaire "Control over action" Yu. Kulya; Temporary Perspective Questionnaire (ZTPI) Zimbaro; Questionnaire "Integral job satisfaction" N. Fetiskin, V. Kozlov, G. Manuilov). The experimental base of the study were students majoring in 053 "Psychology" of Donetsk National University named after Vasyl Stus (n = 92 people) aged 18-22 years.*

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⁵ Doctor of pedagogical sciences, associate professor, professor of the department, of sociology and social work, National University "Lviv Politechnica", Lviv, Ukraine, Tamara.H.Tiurina@lpnu.ua, orcid.org/0000-0001-9421-9350

⁶ Doctor of psychological sciences, professor, Head of the Department of Psychology, Municipal Higher Education Institution "Vinnytsia Academy of Continuing Education", Vinnytsia, Ukraine, lyda1974@gmail.com, orcid.org/0000-0002-6316-2352

⁷ Candidate of pedagogical sciences, associate professor, Senior Lecturer of general and engineering disciplines department, National Academy of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine named after Bohdan Khmelnytskyi, Khmelnytskyi, Ukraine, vikashevchuk71@gmail.com, orcid.org/0000-0002-0436-1183

⁸ Doctor of pedagogical sciences, professor, Head of the English translation department, Faculty of foreign languages and humanities, National Academy of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine named after Bohdan Khmelnytskyi, Khmelnytskyi, Ukraine, i.bloshch@gmail.com, orcid.org/0000-0003-1925-9621

Introduction

The high level of development of human civilization, which is manifested in the achievements of science, technology, medicine and other spheres of human life, research on the capabilities of modern man does not exclude the emergence of new negative phenomena that threaten the overall health of mankind. One of such phenomenon is the phenomenon of procrastination, which has interdisciplinary significance and is the subject of research by psychologists, sociologists, educators and philosophers. First of all, it is necessary to consider and clarify the psychological meaning of the concept of "procrastination" and determine its place in a number of semantically similar psychological concepts.

Higher school instructors' pedagogical and psychological skills improvement for development of students' professional training were substantiated by I. Melnychuk, I. Drozdova, I. Savchak, I. Bloschynskiyi (Melnychuk, Drozdova, Savchak, Bloschynskiyi, 2019). Issues of complex portfolio usage by the future primary school teachers training of the new Ukrainian school were regarded in the work A. Kykylyk, H. Stukan, L. Hlushok, I. Shorobura, I. Bloschynskiyi (Kykylyk, et al, 2020). Some scientists studied the strategic significance of English in self-education of the students for fundamentalization of university education (Melnychuk, Rebukha, Zavgorodnia, Bloschynskiyi, 2018). Some issues on changing the educational paradigm in post-pandemic world were presented in the works of S. Hanaba, O. Mysechko, I. Bloschynskiyi (Hanaba, Mysechko, Bloschynskiyi, 2020). Other scholars L. Borovyk, L. Matokhniuk, K. Demyanyuk, V. Shevchuk, S. Pidhaichuk, O. Danylenko, A. Halimov, I. Bloschynskiyi revealed the peculiarities of professional imagination formation in the process of implementation of technical disciplines with the aid of IT (Borovyk, et al, 2020).

The urgency of the problem of "postponement" of affairs and life in general has led to the emergence of a number of case studies in psychological science. In particular, the features of procrastination and its causes were studied by M. Spada, P. Steele, K. Taylor, K. Lay, N. Milgam and others. Native researchers such as: S. Babatina, E. Bazika, M. Dvornik, S. Sobolev, Y. Shaygorodsky, turned to the study of this phenomenon only in the early 19th century (Demina, Ral'nikova, Luzhbina, 2010). Some scientific researches on the problems of laziness, lack of motivation and willpower, underdevelopment of professional skills, optimization of personal time were conducted in Ukraine, but, of course, they should not be reduced to procrastination (F'ore, 2013).

The term "procrastination" is new to Ukrainian psychology, despite the fact that the psychological essence of this term phenomenon is familiar to each of us. Procrastination (Latin pro - instead of and crastinus - tomorrow) - the tendency to postpone the necessary tasks "for later" or "for tomorrow"; behavioral pattern, in which the implementation of leading activities that are important to man in this period of time, deliberately postponed (Milgram, 1993). The person remains in activity, but its activity is directed on extraneous, insignificant, sometimes simply senseless occupations.

The purpose of the article. The aim of the study is to analyze and determine the psychological characteristics of procrastination, as well as to determine its impact on the formation of professionalism at student age. To achieve the purpose of the study, the following tasks were carried out: 1) to determine the nature and specifics of procrastination development in student age by theoretical analysis; 2) to determine the psychological features and characteristics of the phenomenon of procrastination; 3) to investigate the level of procrastination development in student age; 4) determine the impact of procrastination on the formation of professionalism.

Methodology of Research

Theoretical methods (analysis of scientific and methodological literature of native and foreign authors in psychology); empirical methods (Scale for assessing the need for achievements of Yu. Orlov (F'ore, 2013); Methods of research of volitional self-regulation A. Zverkov, E. Eidman (Pashukova, Dopira, D'yakonov, 1996); Melbourne decision-making questionnaire (adaptation T. Kornilova, S. Kornilova) (Lay, 1986); Methodology "Self-assessment of organization" (Lay, 1986); Questionnaire "Control over action" Yu. Kulya (Raygorodskiy, 2000); Zimbardo Temporary Perspective Questionnaire (ZTPI) (Lay, 1986); Questionnaire "Integral job satisfaction" (N. Fetiskin, V. Kozlov, G. Manuilov) (Fetiskin, 2002); methods of qualitative and quantitative data analysis.

Sample of the study: The experimental base of the study were students majoring in 053 "Psychology" of Donetsk National University named after Vasyl Stus (n = 92 people) aged 18-22 years, of whom 63 people - girls and 29 - boys.

Results of Research

In psychological science, the term "procrastination" was introduced in 1977 by P. Ringenbach in the book "Procrastination in human life". In the

same year, a book by A. Ellis and W. Knaus "Overcoming Procrastination" was published, which was based on clinical observations. Then came the popular science book by J. Burke and L. Yuen "Procrastination: what it is and how to deal with it" (Ferrari, 1995). And mentions of this phenomenon, as well as its formulation can be found even earlier - as in the works of the heyday of the Industrial Revolution - in the middle of the eighteenth century, and in the Oxford Dictionary of 1548. It is also possible to note the existence in most languages of proverbs such as "Do not put off for tomorrow what can be done today." Thus, we can conclude that procrastination has always been. Just as necessary and increasing the urgency of the problem, it began to be studied.

Theories, methods for measuring the level of procrastination, techniques for its weakening have appeared. Everyone at least once in their life did not shy away from performing any actions and postponed them, especially when it was necessary to do something under duress or under pressure of circumstances or when there were doubts about the necessity and usefulness of the intended. But the procrastinator procrastinates even when he is 100% sure of the necessity and importance of action. And he has no doubt that it is necessary, useful, and the idea had to be done "yesterday." But he deliberately postpones the planned case, despite the fact that it will cause some problems and complications. In this case, he can perform small and insignificant tasks, which he attaches more importance.

Procrastination can cause stress, guilt, decreased productivity, and dissatisfaction with others due to failure and fulfill obligations. The combination of these feelings and the effort can provoke further procrastination. Chronic procrastination can be caused by a hidden psychological or physiological illness. Some people can work productively only when a strict time frame is set, the peak of their productivity is in the last hours and minutes before the deadline. The main signs of procrastination are the lack of productivity and meaning in combination with the constant deposition of really important and useful things. To some extent, this is not a bad thing, because no one can work like a machine. Short breaks for rest and change of activity have a positive effect on overall productivity (Palladino, 2015). Procrastination is a kind of expression of an emotional reaction to planned or necessary things (Kornilova, 2003). Depending on the nature of these emotions, procrastination is divided into two fundamental types: "relaxed", when a person spends time on other, more enjoyable activities and entertainment, and "tense", associated with general overload, loss of sense of time, dissatisfaction with their own achievements, unclear life goals, indecision and self-doubt (Lay, 1986).

In the conditions of a modern society which puts forward serious requirements to independence and responsibility of the person, urgency of a problem of the described phenomenon grows (Maksymenko, Matokhnyuk, 2017). According to psychologists who study this phenomenon, persistent procrastination is present in 15-25% of the world's population. Moreover, as longitudinal studies show, over the past 25 years, the level of procrastination has increased and tends to increase further (Vorob'eva, 2013).

N. Milgram and co-authors first identified five types of procrastination: 1) daily (household), ie postponement of household chores, which must be performed regularly; 2) procrastination in decision-making (including minor); 3) neurotic - postponement of vital decisions, such as choosing a profession or starting a family; 4) compulsive, when a person combines two types of procrastination - daily and in decision-making; 5) academic, ie postponement of educational tasks, preparation for exams, etc (Demina, Ral'nikova, Luzhbina, 2010). There are also procrastination associated with the desire to avoid unpleasant business and with the receipt of acute experiences in a shortage of time. In this regard, there are two types of procrastinators - passive and active. The active procrastinator tends to increase the voltage. Postponing cases "to the last", it creates a critical moment associated with the extreme proximity of the deadline. When there is little time to complete the work, a person experiences mobilization of forces, full concentration, increased activity of mental processes (Il'in, 2011).

Analyzing and summarizing foreign studies of procrastination, we can talk about the presence of 3 main components of this phenomenon: behavioral, cognitive and emotional. Procrastination is a complex, psychologically heterogeneous phenomenon that includes behavioral, emotional and cognitive components closely related to the motivational sphere of personality. The behavioral component of procrastination is seen as a form of learning. Students tend to avoid tasks that they find unpleasant and repulsive and engage in short-term activities that seem more important to them than those that require more time to complete (Bazyka, 2003). Such behavior may well be seen as a way to avoid responsibility or anxiety associated with learning. It can also be associated with voltage (Dvornyk, 2014).

Procrastination can be considered as a result of cognitive impairment, these problems are not related to abilities or level of intelligence, but procrastinators have difficulties in perception and adequate assessment of time (Fetiskin, 2002). The relationship with the emotional sphere was revealed in the course of research on procrastination: 1) with the fear of failure and neuroticism; 2) with impulsivity (Blunt, Pychyl, 2000).

Procrastinators often have perfectionist attitudes that apply to all spheres of life. On the other hand, there are impulsive procrastinators, who have difficulty in perceiving and evaluating signals coming from the environment. Such people are unable to postpone the satisfaction of their own needs, have difficulty with self-control. A number of authors also highlight the fourth component - the subconscious. Sometimes procrastination can signal the presence of deep intrapersonal conflicts (Demina, Ral'nikova, Luzhbina, 2010). A person can unconsciously avoid and delay the performance of any activity that has a certain symbolic meaning for him. Such activity on an unconscious level is associated with some conflict in the past and is seen as a threat.

Therefore, we can note that procrastination is a complex phenomenon that includes: behavioral component (procrastination as a fixed mechanism of human behavior), cognitive component (specificity of feeling the results of activities, as well as motivation to perform activities), emotional component (high anxiety, emotional congestion, fear of failure and neuroticism), as well as the subconscious component (procrastination as a protective mechanism of the individual, which works when increasing anxiety and assessing the situation of any task as threatening and danger).

Modern society makes high demands on the responsibility, independence and productivity of the individual (Maksymenko, Matokhnyuk, 2017). And the study of procrastination is a very significant and relevant, especially when there are problems and difficulties that can not be attributed to human laziness and disinterest in performing the necessary activities. Thus, the phenomenon of procrastination is a complex psychological concept that should not be completely identified with the protective mechanisms or violations of motivational and volitional processes. This issue requires further study and in-depth research that will clarify the available data on the nature of procrastination, its components and possible correlations with other psychological characteristics of the individual.

Student's age is a special period of human life. According to B. Ananiev, it is a sensitive period for the development of basic sociogenic potentials of human. Higher education has a huge impact on the human psyche, the development of his personality. During their studies at the university, in the presence of favorable conditions, students develop all levels of the psyche. They determine the direction of the human mind, ie form the composition of thinking that characterizes the professional orientation of the individual. Successful studying at higher education establishment requires a fairly high level of general intellectual development,

including perception, memory, thinking, attention, level of mastery of a certain range of logical operations. Considering students as a special social category, a specific community of people, I. Zimova identifies the main characteristics of student's age that distinguish it from other groups with high educational level, high cognitive motivation, the highest social activity and a very harmonious combination of intellectual and social maturity. In terms of general mental development, students at a period of intensive socialization of personality, the development of higher mental functions, the formation of the entire intellectual system and the individual as a whole. It is the entrance to the university that creates in a young person a sense of faith in his own abilities and determines his future life. However, further study at the university also reveals changes in the mood of young people: the euphoria of the first months of study is replaced by skepticism about teaching, the assessment system and so on. However, it should be noted that the ability to arbitrarily and consciously regulate their behavior is not fully developed in young people. The success of a young person's educational activities is determined by the development of new features of his studies at the university. In the process of learning the student body is formed, skills and abilities of organizational work are developed, the system of work on development of professionally significant qualities of the person is formed.

Thus, the student age is characterized by the achievement of the highest, peak results, which are based on all previous processes of biological, psychological, social development. At the same time, the beginning of studying at higher education al establishment is a highly stressful period of life: it presents a critical life event (change in the stage of the life cycle), in some universities there are intense daily educational overloads.

V. Bykova, studying the features of student procrastination, argues that the causes and features of procrastination in students and adults are different. Procrastination occurs most often in situations and cases involving intellectual stress, requiring self-organization and planning of activities characterized by delayed remuneration, lack of motivation, the need to interact with people who cause negative emotions. Among the causes of student's procrastination syndrome, she says: is unfavorite job, boring and unpleasant thing to do; inability to set priorities; ambiguity of the main life goals, own directions; inability to organize themselves and their time; lack of motivation; insecurity (Milgram, 1992).

Causes, types of procrastination and its consequences are widely reflected in foreign literature. Conducting a generalized theoretical analysis on this issue, there are several approaches to the study of this phenomenon, in particular, researchers identify five types of procrastination: 1.

Procrastination as a life tactic - lack of skills in performing daily, routine duties, which are observed throughout life and are associated with the inability to manage time. 2. Procrastination in decision-making - the inability to accept decision in a certain period. 3. Neurotic procrastination - inability to take in time vital - careful decisions. 4. Compulsive procrastination - a chronic delay in behavior. 5. Academic procrastination - difficulties in completing tasks at the right time during training (Demina, Ral'nikova, Luzhbina, 2010).

The main causes of academic procrastination are: lack of motivation and in a broad sense - a violation of the motivational-volitional sphere, stress as a consequence of uncertainty and fear of the future, or, conversely, perfectionism. But the most common reasons are the inability to build a hierarchy of goals and values and plan their activities, lack of direct communication with the environment and the excess of virtual (Silistraru et al., 2021). According to research by S. Mokhova and A. Nevryuyev, the main causes of academic procrastination are: disease, social and family problems, lack of motivation and interest, overconfidence, laziness, lack of guidance and advice from teachers, helplessness, low level of communication, external distractions. This often leads to lower performance, increased anxiety, often - to the formation of inferiority complex and, as a result, to the refusal of further training. Therefore, to reduce the level of academic procrastination, teachers need to be more attentive to students, introduce an effective system of incentives, promote the development of academic ties between students and logically divide certain types of work into smaller components.

In the study of causal relationships of this phenomenon in humans, many researchers have concluded that the key factors can be considered features of human personality and the characteristics of the tasks themselves (Varvaricheva, 2014). Analyzing the causes of procrastination together with the quality of the tasks themselves, most authors identify the following reasons: the imposition of tasks from the outside; delayed consequences; long term given for execution; large temporary investments in the task; boring, routine tasks; high employment in others matters; deferment in receiving pleasure or rewards.

Depending on the emotional response, scientists distinguish two fundamental types of procrastinators: 1. "Relaxed" procrastinator spends time on other, more enjoyable, activities and entertainment. Their procrastination is a form of escape from the unpleasant experiences of doing what they put off. At first they do not do it because they are bored, and then they look for excuses or come up with pseudo-rational explanations for their behavior. At the heart of their motives may be the desire to meet the most

important emotional needs in the attention and approval of others, in love, self-confidence. 2. "Intense" procrastinator is characterized by general overload, loss of sense of time, dissatisfaction with their own achievements, unclear life goals. Fear of failure (fear that you will fail due to lack of necessary knowledge (talent, luck), fear of demonstrating incompetence are the most common causes of this type of procrastination. Too self-critical people avoid many forms of activity, especially if they have an element of competition. They realize that giving up the fight is also a form of defeat, and they also suffer because of it. However, defeat without a fight is obviously less painful than the failure of a real attempt. Fear of success is no less common cause of academic procrastination. This phenomenon is often formed during the school years and is manifested in the desire to be worse and less successful in order to maintain certain relationships with friends, to meet certain stereotypes or to prevent additional workload and increased demands from teachers and parents. Often this trend persists in some students in the junior year while studying at the university. Another reason for academic procrastination is resistance to external control. Procrastinators of this type interact with reality in a "passive-aggressive" way. Deep down, they believe that their desires are the law, and any demands on them (from relatives, teachers, leaders, comrades) cause, respectively, protest and revolt. But the vast majority of researchers believe that the main cause of procrastination in the student environment is a lack of motivation to learn. This is due to various factors: they entered the university only at the request of parents, do not see prospects in future professional activities, the main purpose of education are to obtain a diploma.

Among the main causes of procrastination are: authoritarianism of parents, procrastination may be a response to the authoritarian style of parenting; fear of failure - a person is afraid that he will not cope with the task, he is afraid that he does not have enough abilities, skills or time. "It's better not to do it at all than to look ridiculous," the procrastinator thinks. Low self-esteem, self-doubt - that's what prevents; perfectionism - a person does not accept average results. If you start a business, then do it perfectly; unclear goals - if the leader did not indicate in which direction to move, but explained that there are no priorities and most importantly, the person is completely confused and seeks to delay the implementation of unclear tasks, he just does not know from which side to approach the problem, and as nature is indecisive, he is afraid to take responsibility; not true beliefs - a person thinks that if you drive it into the framework, he can do the job much better; laziness and lack of interest.

The consequences of procrastination are stress, guilt, loss of productivity, dissatisfaction with others due to non-fulfillment of obligations. In an effort to complete the task in a limited period of time, a person experiences serious emotional and physical stress. Nervous tension, constant sleep deprivation, abuse of caffeine, energy drinks - all this can have unpleasant consequences on the body. In addition, procrastination is the basis for feelings of guilt because of unfinished work, lack of self-realization, loss of opportunities, etc. and is the result of poor self-control. Time management techniques and time planning skills help to combat this phenomenon. Equally important is the development of the student's desire to succeed, which will reduce feelings of anxiety and fear of failure (Milgram, 1995).

Thus, the main causes of academic procrastination are: illness, social and family problems, lack of motivation and interest in learning, overconfidence, laziness, poor management of teaching activities and teacher advice, helplessness of individual students, lack of direct communication and excess of virtual, external distractions. Procrastination leads to a decrease in the quality of success, increase the level of anxiety, and sometimes - to the refusal of further training. Procrastination does not become an obstacle if it is temporary and, conversely, grows into a problem becoming chronic. Chronic procrastination interferes with work, success, plans for the future. It can be a hidden beginning of a psychological or physical illness. Chronic procrastination is characteristic of students who have chosen the wrong profession and educational institution; they study without interest, hence the sleepless nights trying to do unpleasant tasks on the last day before tests, exams. The decision to leave the study of an uninteresting specialty can be made only by a strong personality, with a strong character, but only a few are capable of radical actions (Kovylin, 2013). Thus, procrastination is a process of voluntary evasion of important tasks and, instead, the performance of things that are less important, but those that bring quick results and satisfaction ("here and now"). Procrastination usually leads to negative consequences both personally and professionally.

Using the methodology "Scale for assessing the need for achievements" (Yu. Orlova) (F'ore, 2013) we determine what levels of achievement motivation prevail in students. This technique diagnoses three levels of achievement needs: low, medium and high motivational level. Statistical analysis of the obtained results was performed using Excel spreadsheets.

From Fig. 1 it is seen that the predominant level of need for achievements according to the method of "Scale of need for achievements" by Yu. Orlov is: medium level - 84% (4-7 points), with a low level - 14% (1-3 points) and high - 2% (8-10 points).

Fig. 1. Percentage distribution of motivational levels of achievements according to the method "Scale of needs assessment for achievements (Yu. Orlova)

Individuals with a strong need for achievement are more effective and avoid routine work. They tend to look for more efficient tasks. Researchers have always believed that people with a strong need for achievement should pay more attention to personal responsibility for performance, because only then can they feel satisfied with what they have done better than others.

Students are future professionals who not only study, but also show themselves up in various ways in social and cultural life. That is, they have an active position in life and the desire to succeed. These results can be explained by the continuous development of technology, the rapid pace of life, competition and other social factors that force us to adapt constantly to change. Free opportunity for higher education, increasing the quality of life, increasing aspirations and ambitions, lack of time - all this stimulates a person to develop motivation to succeed as a tool through which he will fight for a better "place under the sun".

In general, the need to achieve is a stable characteristic of the individual, ie manifested in a wide range of situations, regardless of their specific content. The motivation to succeed, the goal is expressed in the desire to improve results, perseverance in achieving their goals, and affects the entire life of the individual.

We have determined that people with an average level of need for achievement are quite confident in coping with tasks of medium severity,

but do not like situations involving risk. Because a person needs to have a high need for achievement to be successful, this need can and should be developed, because this is an important trait inherent in leaders.

Using the method of studying volitional self-regulation A. Zverkova, E. Eidman (Pashukova, Dopira, D'yakonov, 1996), we determined the levels of volitional self-regulation on a common scale and two subscales: persistence and self-control.

Fig. 2. Percentage distribution of indicators of low and high levels separately for each scale according to the method of Zverkov & Eidman

In general, the volitional self-regulation level means the degree of mastering their behavior and actions control in different situations. A high level on the common scale (35%) is inherent in individuals who are self-sufficient and emotionally mature. They are characterized by calmness, a pronounced socio-positive orientation and self-confidence. There is an infrequent increase in internal tensions associated with the desire to control every step, stage of their own behavior. Spontaneous actions lead to a state of anxiety. Low level on this scale is observed in 65% of people. These people are sensual, vulnerable and emotionally unstable. They are characterized by a low level of reflexivity, and the general background of activity is usually reduced.

High level on the subscale of persistence was found in 45% of people. This characterizes the strength of a person's intentions - his desire to complete the work started. On the positive pole, they are active, hard-working people who actively strive to do what is planned, are mobilized by obstacles and barriers to the goal, but, at the same time, are distracted by alternatives and temptations, their main value - the case is started. Otherwise - a possible loss of flexibility of behavior, the presence of manic tendencies. Low values on this scale (55%) indicate increased lability, and uncertainty of

the subjects. This can lead to inconsistencies and even chaotic behavior. The reduced background of working capacity and activity is balanced by increased sensitivity and ingenuity, as well as tendency to free interpretation of social norms.

A high level on the subscale of self-control was found in 37% of people and gained by emotionally stable people who are well-versed in various situations. Usually these people are emotionally stable, self-confident, they are characterized by inner peace, lack of fear of the unknown, willingness to accept the new, unexpected, tendencies to innovation and radicalism. The desire for constant self-control, excessive conscious restriction of spontaneity can cause increased tension and the benefits of constant fatigue and anxiety. A low level on the same scale (63%) characterizes spontaneity and impulsiveness, combined with preference and abusiveness for traditional views. It separates a person from intense experiences and internal conflicts, contributes to a calm mood.

There is an ambiguous social desirability of high performance on a given scale. The high level of development of volitional self-regulation may be associated with problems in the organization of people life and relationships. Low levels of intrusiveness and self-control usually perform a compensatory function. However, this may be evidence of a violation of the development of personality traits and respond adequately to different situations. Using the Melbourne Decision-Making Questionnaire (adapted by T. Kornilova, S. Kornilova) (MOPR) (Lay, 1986), it was determined how and which strategies of the subjects are guided by in decision-making.

According to the provided histogram (Fig. 3), we see that the scale 1 "Vigilance" and scale 4 over "Vigilance" have almost the same percentage of low and high rates. But these 2 categories should be distinguished, although at first glance they have the same meaning. The category of vigilance means that such a person is quite attentive and constantly vigilant. And vigilance is a manifestation of extreme caution, even when a person is in a safe situation. According to this method, these concepts are characterized as follows: vigilance - is the main stylistic characteristic of man as a person who makes decisions related to cognitive complexity, the need for knowledge and tolerance for uncertainty; vigilance is an unjustified "throwing" between different alternatives, an impulsive acceptance that promises to get rid of the situation; in extreme forms - "panic" in choosing between alternatives. Scale 2 "Avoidance" indicates that more than half of the respondents avoid independent decision-making, shift responsibilities and rationalize questionable alternatives. This is because a person either adapts to a problem or decision, or avoids it. She is afraid to take responsibility or just does not

want to, and such a person will always find excuses. On a scale of 3 "Procrastination", most subjects received high scores - that is, they are characterized by a high level of development of procrastination. This is a tendency to constant postpone or so-called postponement of decisions, cases for later. If this is not fought immediately, then in the future such people become prone to constant postponement of cases, negative thoughts and actions for later. Although the previous 3 traits, such as vigilance, avoidance and over vigilance, can be corrected or reduced. Procrastination can develop into a disease and become a lifestyle of the individual.

Fig. 3. Percentage distribution of indicators of low and high levels separately for each scale according to the method of MOPR (T. Kornilova, S. Kornilova)

The manifestations of all these phenomena can be influenced by a number of circumstances, for example: previously experienced stress or a situation that is not pleasant to a person, which had an unpleasant "sediment" and now it manifests itself in this way. Such phenomena can also include a high level of anxiety associated with previous personal experience. In most situations, a person is driven by emotions, so emotions affect people in many different ways. The same emotion affects people differently; moreover, it has different effects on the same person who gets into different situations. Therefore, depending on what situations a person has been in before, how he fought with them and got out of them, so he will react to all life events, circumstances and solve their problems based on past experience. The scale of procrastination for students of S. Leigh (Lay, 1986) was determined by the levels of development of procrastination in students.

For Fig. 4 shows that the average level of procrastination development - 81% is predominant among students, they also have a high level of procrastination development - it is 6% and low 13%. Procrastination is a painful inability to take action, accompanied by anxiety, sadness and anxiety. This is an endless postponement of important and urgent tasks for later. If a lazy person just rejoices when he manages to rest for a few hours, then in the case of procrastination the opposite effect occurs: the person is depressed by his inaction and still can not force himself to take up the cause. Sometimes a person despairs, just disappointed with himself and still does not move. The worst thing is that many of them are in this state for weeks and months. The consequences of procrastination can be very sad.

Fig.4. The results of an empirical study by the method of the Scale of procrastination for students (S. Leia)

Procrastination occurs often in situations and cases involving intellectual stress, requiring self-organization and planning of activities characterized by delayed remuneration, lack of motivation, the need to interact with people who cause negative emotions. Among the causes of procrastination syndrome among students are the following: un favorite job, boring and unpleasant thing to do; inability to set priorities; ambiguity of the main life goals, own directions; inability to organize themselves and their time; lack of motivation; insecurity. The main reasons for the development of academic procrastination include: illness, social and family problems, lack of motivation and interest in learning, overconfidence, laziness, poor leadership of educational activities and teacher advice, helplessness of individual students, lack of direct communication and excess of virtual, external distractional factors. Procrastination leads to a decrease in the quality of success, increase the level of anxiety, and sometimes - to the refusal of further training.

According to the method of "Assessment of self-organization" (Lay, 1986) the following results were obtained:

Fig. 5. The results of empirical research on the method of "Self-assessment of organization"

In Fig. 5 is shown that in a larger number of subjects the organization is developed at the average level - 63%, high level - 27% and low level is inherent in only 10%.

The high rate is characterized by high demands of the individual to himself and focus on the result. Such a person realizes what his ultimate goal is and what needs to be done to achieve it. Organization, which is at high level, is an acquired skill that must be systematically maintained. Successful people know that as soon as they deviate from the rules and give up these promises, they will automatically leave the organization. A person can be successful only when he keeps himself within limits.

The average level is characterized by the presence of constant throws between high activity and a significant decline. A person experiences a state of internal struggle and additional stress from the fact that he can not allocate time and a lot of effort is wasted.

The low rate is characterized by a reluctance to act at all. Maybe such a person sometimes wants to change something in his life, but he has too little internal reserves to achieve the desired.

According to the questionnaire "Control over action" Yu. Kulya (Raygorodskiy, 2000) the following results were obtained:

Fig. 6. The results of empirical research on the method of "Control of action" Yu. Kulya

Control over the action associated with decision-making (when planning). This scale reflects the ability of the subject in the process of initiating the action to distract from the inferior, competing intentions.

Control over the action associated with the implementation (in the implementation). This scale reflects the ability of the subject to be in the process of realization of intentions for the necessary time, to keep the focus of actual intention, to show persistence.

Action control associated with a focus on failure (when planning). This scale reflects the ability of the subject to initiate the process of realization of the intention, despite the accompanying difficulties.

The results of this method show that a small percentage of respondents (29% with 100% on the scale of "planning") plan their activities and a very large percentage of people (83% with 100% on the scale of "failure") are afraid of failures and difficulties and half of the subjects still realize their intentions, and half do not, because the fear of failure and possible inability to plan prevail over them.

High scores on each of the scales mean focus on action, and low in turn - focus on their own condition and experience. According to the ZTPI method Questionnaire of time perspective F. Zimbardo (Milgram, 2000), the following results were obtained:

Fig. 7. The results of empirical research on the method F. Zimbardo "Questionnaire of time perspective"

The factor "Negative past" reflects the general pessimistic, negative or mixed aversion to the past. May involve trauma, pain and regret. This attitude can be due to real unpleasant and traumatic events, due to the negative reconstruction of positive events, or due to both of them.

The factor "Hedonistic mood" - reflects the hedonistic, risky, "I don't care" attitude to time and life. Provides a focus on pleasure, excitement, enjoyment in the present and a lack of concern for future consequences or sacrifices in favor of future rewards.

Future Factor Reflects the general focus on the future. Assumes that behavior is largely determined by the desire for goals and rewards for the future. Characterized by planning and achieving future goals.

The "Positive Past" factor reflects a warm, sentimental attitude toward one's past. This indicator is characterized by a nostalgic, positive reconstruction of the past; it is presented in a rainbow light.

Factor "Fatalistic Present" Reveals a fatalistic, helpless and hopeless attitude towards one's future and life in general. This factor reflects the lack of a focused time perspective. There is a lack of focus on future-oriented goals, no emphasis on excitement, and no nostalgia or bitterness for the past. This factor reveals the belief that their future cannot be influenced by individual actions; people with high scores on this scale are in the power of capricious (demanding) fate.

Using the method of the Questionnaire "Integral job satisfaction" (N. Fetiskin, V. Kozlov, G. Manuilov) (Fetiskin, 2002) the following results were obtained:

Fig. 8. The results of an empirical study on the method of the questionnaire "Integral job satisfaction" (N. Fetiskin, V. Kozlov, G. Manuilov)

This chart shows that the average level of job satisfaction is average - 72%, high reaches 23%, and low - 5%.

This means that most respondents are still satisfied with their profession, working conditions, relationships with management and staff. Job satisfaction is a state of balance of the requirements shown by the worker to the maintenance, character and working conditions, and a subjective estimation of possibilities of realization of these requirements. Job satisfaction - is the evaluative attitude of a person or group of people to their own work, its various aspects and the most important indicator of employee adaptation in the organization.

Labor - is a purposeful human activity, in the process of which it affects nature and uses it to produce material goods needed to meet their needs. Work is one of the basic conditions of human life and society. It is labor activity that underlies any social relations and significantly affects the relations and interactions of people. In addition, it is of great importance to be in the process of personality formation.

In the process of labor and social activity a person shows a different degree of activity, which is due to its interests and needs.

Correlation analysis was performed using the program SPSS Statistics 13. * - the correlation is significant at 0.05 (bilateral); ** - correlation is significant at the level of 0.01 (bilateral).

1. Perseverance and self-control (474 **) - these two categories are the volitional qualities of the individual. Persistence is a strong-willed quality due to which a person can mobilize his forces for a relatively long and difficult struggle with obstacles and difficulties encountered in his activities

on the way to achieving quite distant goals. Without perseverance, without standing his ground and fighting for the implementation of the decision, there can be no determination, independence, self-control and determination. Self-control is a volitional quality characteristic of people who control their thoughts and feelings, their actions and needs. People who are characterized by self-control, balance and consistent.

Also, these two categories are inevitably associated with procrastination. That is, the more developed are these qualities, the less is the development of procrastination in the individual.

2. Procrastination and avoidance (442 **) - these two categories are also inextricably linked. Avoiding decision-making, shifting responsibility to others - this is procrastination. The person avoids work, postpones everything for later. Thus these two concepts are inextricably linked.

3. Vigilance and over vigilance (477 **) - these two categories should be distinguished, although at first glance they have the same meaning. The category of over vigilance means that such a person is quite attentive and constantly vigilant. And vigilance is a manifestation of extreme caution, even when a person is in a safe situation. Vigilance is the main stylistic characteristic of a person as a person who makes decisions related to cognitive complexity, the need for knowledge and tolerance for uncertainty; over vigilance is an unjustified "throwing" between different alternatives, an impulsive acceptance that promises to get rid of the situation; in extreme forms - "panic" in choosing between alternatives.

4. Implementation and organization (478 **) - this connection can be explained by the fact that these qualities of the individual that characterize his ability to plan wisely, organize their activities and be sure to carry it out. Such people follow the order in work, rationally distribute their time, clearly plan and perform everything.

5. Organization and interest in work (305 **) - if a person has an interest in this type of profession and it is very organized, then he will achieve great success in his profession. Such individuals have a business orientation and enjoy the process of work.

6. Avoidance and vigilance (277 *) - vigilance is the main stylistic characteristic of man as a person who makes decisions related to cognitive complexity, the need for knowledge and tolerance for uncertainty. Clarification of the goals and objectives of the solution, consideration of alternatives associated with the search for information, its assimilation "without prejudice" and evaluation before the choice. Avoidance of independent decision-making, transfer of responsibility and rationalization of dubious alternatives.

7. Planning and implementation (312 *) - the ability of the individual in the process of initiating action to be distracted from the inferior, competing. Realization is the ability of a person to be in the process of realizing the intention for the necessary time, to keep the focus of the actual intention, to show perseverance. These concepts are closely interconnected and mean the ability to reasonably plan, organize their activities and be sure to carry it out.

Conclusions

Each phenomenon has its causes. The reasons that provoke the development of such a phenomenon as procrastination, we can include not only external causes but also internal. Some causes are due to depressive disorder, but this is rare. Usually the reasons forcing a person to put things off indefinitely are referred to as simpler. One of the most common causes of pathological inability to act is fear. We have been taught since childhood that mistakes are bad; they should be avoided in all possible ways. Most often, procrastination occurs as a result of fear of action. Another reason for the lack of motivation to act is the internal dissatisfaction with the activities that have to be engaged. It's no secret that many people spend their entire lives hating their work. This reason can be attributed to student activities. Dissatisfaction with the monotonous work, and even more so the work that has to be done independently provokes the development of the phenomenon of procrastination. In some cases, the human brain is so overloaded that it simply cannot work effectively. The cause of procrastination is often severe emotional exhaustion, increasing nervous tension, and as a result stress.

An empirical study of student procrastination has shown that students are more characterized by an average level of procrastination. 6% of students had a high level of procrastination; 81% have an average level, 13% of students have a low level of procrastination. Thus, among student youth there is a tendency to postpone the execution of cases for later. The activity of such students is aimed at meaningless, insignificant activities, while there are important tasks that require immediate completion. They are characterized by preparation for the exam as soon as possible before passing, postponing important cases and decisions to a later date. We also found the imposition of tasks from the outside; delayed consequences; long term given for execution; large temporary investments in the task; boring, routine tasks; high employment in other matters; deferment in receiving pleasure or rewards.

It is important among student youth to conduct conversations on relevant topics, to clarify problem-solving classes, to conduct trainings on the formation of students' temporal competence, to inform about the techniques and methods of effective self-organization and life time management. After all, chronic procrastination, which is often observed in student's age, is a destructive form of personality behavior in relation to the organization of their own space. Student must understand that first of all his motivation to study, the acquisition of professional knowledge will help to combat the phenomenon of procrastination. Therefore, any intention, goal, built plan must be specific, realistic, achievable, flexible, measurable, focused and time-bound.

Prospects for further research: Need further study of the impact of individual psychological and personal qualities on the development of procrastination in young people.

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